

Auditing Token Padding and Token Accounting in Large Language Models: A Constraint-Adherence Metric and a Multi-Provider Empirical Study

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Abstract

Large language models (LLMs) frequently emit more tokens than a task requires, inflating cost and latency even when the extra text adds no information and violates explicit user constraints. We introduce the *Token Padding Index* (TPI), a reference-anchored metric that penalises verbosity, constraint violation, and semantic drift relative to a minimal control answer, plus an optional correctness term. We pair TPI with an adversarial battery of 106 *trap* prompts—each carrying an explicit negative constraint (e.g. “answer with a single word; no explanation”)—and audit seven production models across three providers (OpenAI, Google, Anthropic) over 6970 trials. Our central finding is a dissociation between the tokens a provider *bills* and the content a model *generates*. On raw provider tokens the three Anthropic models appear extreme—3.6–3.8× the control—but re-counting every response with one shared tokenizer collapses them to 1.09–1.28×, comparable to OpenAI and Gemini. We trace this to token *accounting*: the single word “Tokyo” is billed as 1 completion token by OpenAI and 7 by Anthropic for character-identical text (with zero reported thinking tokens) under the provider accounting we observed in mid-2026. This provides evidence for *two separable sources of token overhead*—content verbosity and tokenizer-accounting—and shows raw cross-provider token audits are misleading unless normalised: after normalisation only 1 of 21 model pairs differs significantly, versus 15 of 21 on raw tokens. We release the metric, trap battery, and pipeline as open source.

1 Introduction

In recent times, Large Language Models (LLMs) are increasingly being used across different contexts from coding assistants, search systems, customer support, and autonomous agents, where every generated token contributes to latency, computational cost, and energy consumption. While recent research has focused extensively on reasoning ability, instruction following, and safety, comparatively little attention has been paid to whether models generate only the information users explicitly request. Even seemingly minor verbosity, when repeated across millions of API calls, translates into substantial operational costs. We refer to this unnecessary generation as *token padding*.

Consider a user who asks “Reply with only the city name” and receives “Of course! The capital of Japan is Tokyo. Let me know if you need anything else!” The user has paid—in tokens, latency, and money—for content they explicitly declined. This behaviour, which we call *token padding*, is

Figure 1: ATAP at a glance. Every response is counted twice: once with a *shared* tokenizer, yielding a *Content TPI* that reflects what the model actually generated, and once with each *provider’s* tokenizer, yielding a *Billing TPI* that reflects what a practitioner is charged. The gap between the two is the tokenizer-accounting overhead a single-tokenizer audit cannot see.

pervasive: chat-tuned models are optimised for helpfulness and tend to add greetings, restatements, caveats, and explanatory scaffolding regardless of instructions to the contrary, a tendency reinforced by length bias in preference-based fine-tuning [3]. At scale, padding is a direct and measurable tax on every API call.

Measuring token padding is not as simple as counting tokens. Some tasks legitimately require longer responses, while others demand strict brevity. A useful evaluation framework must therefore distinguish necessary information from unnecessary verbosity while accounting for correctness, semantic fidelity, and explicit instruction compliance. Existing evaluation benchmarks do not directly address this problem.

This paper makes three contributions:

1. **The Token Padding Index (TPI)**—a reference-anchored metric (Section 3) that scores an answer well only when it is simultaneously concise, compliant, and faithful.
2. **An adversarial trap battery**—106 prompts across four padding archetypes (Section 4), each with machine-checkable constraints and, where applicable, a deterministic answer key [1].
3. **A multi-provider empirical study**—6970 trials over seven production models from three providers (Sections 5–6) that separates a model’s *content* padding from the *tokenizer-accounting* overhead a raw provider-token audit would wrongly attribute to it.

These contributions form a deliberate hierarchy: the metric and the auditing pipeline that operationalises it are the *methodology*, and the empirical study is their *payoff*—applying the method uncovers two distinct sources of token overhead, one arising from the *content* a model generates and one from the *provider accounting* applied to that content. The two-source finding is thus a consequence of the methodology rather than a stand-alone anecdote; Figure 1 previews the split.

2 Related Work

Instruction following and constraint benchmarks. A growing line of work measures whether models obey explicit instructions. IFEval [1] scores “verifiable instructions” such as length and format constraints, and FollowBench [2] grades multi-level fine-grained constraints. These benchmarks ask *whether* a constraint is met; ATAP additionally asks at *what token cost* a model meets (or violates) a *negative* constraint, anchoring that cost to a minimal reference.

Length and verbosity bias. Chat models are tuned with human or AI preference signals that systematically favour longer outputs. Length bias in RLHF is documented by Singhal et al. [3]; verbosity bias in LLM-based preference labelling by Saito et al. [4]; and the underlying preference-optimisation recipes by Stiennon et al. [5] and Ouyang et al. [6]. This literature explains *why* padding arises; ATAP supplies a metric to *quantify* its token cost under explicit anti-verbosity instructions.

Evaluation methodology and tokenization. Holistic evaluation frameworks [7] and surveys [8] stress multi-metric, reproducible measurement, and the LLM-as-judge paradigm [9] is now common—though we deliberately avoid it for our compliance and correctness terms in favour of deterministic checks. Tokenization choices materially affect token counts and cost: subword schemes [11], cross-provider vocabulary differences [12], and cross-language tokenizer unfairness [13] all imply that raw provider-token comparisons conflate content with accounting—precisely the confound our tokenizer-normalised TPI isolates.

3 The Token Padding Index

We audit a *target* model against a *control*: the same prompt issued to a baseline model under a strict anti-padding system instruction. The control defines a minimal, task-appropriate reference answer, which lets us separate “long because the task is hard” from “long because the model padded.” To reduce dependence on a single draw, the control is the *shortest valid* of $N = 3$ sampled candidates—a practical approximation of an oracle-minimum answer rather than a claim of true minimality.

For a given prompt let T_t and T_c be the completion-token counts of the target and control responses, let $A \in [0, 1]$ be the target’s *constraint adherence* (the fraction of the prompt’s machine-checkable constraints it satisfies), and let $S \in [0, 1]$ be the *semantic similarity* between the target and control answers. The Token Padding Index is

$$\text{TPI} = \frac{T_t}{T_c} (1 + (1 - A) + (1 - S)). \quad (1)$$

The leading factor T_t/T_c is the raw verbosity ratio. The bracketed term is a multiplicative penalty: it equals 1 for a perfectly compliant, semantically faithful answer and grows as the target either breaks constraints ($A < 1$) or drifts from the reference meaning ($S < 1$). Thus $\text{TPI} \approx 1$ denotes an ideal response—as concise as the minimal reference, fully compliant, and correct—while $\text{TPI} > 1$ quantifies padding, non-compliance, or both. Values below 1 are possible and meaningful: they indicate a target that is *terser* than the control while remaining compliant and faithful.

3.1 Design rationale: why a multiplicative form

The verbosity ratio is the natural unit of cost: each extra completion token is billed and adds latency, so cost grows *linearly* in length, motivating the leading T_t/T_c factor. The remaining quality terms are not independent costs to be *added*; they modulate whether the spent tokens were warranted. We

therefore make them *multiply* the ratio. An additive surrogate such as $\alpha T_t/T_c + \beta(1-A) + \gamma(1-S)$ lets a strong score on one axis mask a failure on another—a perfectly terse but constraint-violating answer could still score well—and forces arbitrary unit-bridging weights between “tokens” and “compliance.” Multiplication keeps the index dimensionless and couples the axes: padding is penalised *in proportion* to how non-compliant or unfaithful the output is, so a long answer that also breaks a rule is worse than the sum of its parts. The penalty is anchored at 1 (no penalty) and each deficit $(1-A)$, $(1-S)$ enters symmetrically, so no axis is privileged. We tie the metric to the family $\text{TPI} = \frac{T_t}{T_c}(1 + \sum_i(1 - X_i))$ over quality scores X_i , and report ablations (Section 6.6) that remove each term to show its empirical contribution.

An axiomatic view. Rather than tune weights, we pin down the functional form by requiring a few properties and taking the simplest function that satisfies them. Write $\text{TPI} = \rho P$ with cost ratio $\rho = T_t/T_c$ and quality penalty $P = g(A, S)$ over scores $X_i \in \{A, S\}$, and require: (i) *identity*—a perfect answer ($A = S = 1$) is unpenalised, $P = 1$, so TPI reduces to the pure cost ratio ρ ; (ii) *monotonicity*— P is non-increasing in each X_i , so degrading any quality axis never improves the score; (iii) *symmetry*—the axes enter through identical slots, so no quality dimension is privileged a priori; (iv) *separability*—each deficit $(1 - X_i)$ contributes additively, so terms can be added or dropped (as in our ablations) without reshaping the others; and (v) *scale invariance*— P is dimensionless, so the index is comparable across prompts and providers. The minimal function meeting (i)–(v) with unit first-order sensitivity is $P = 1 + \sum_i(1 - X_i)$, exactly the bracketed term of Eq. (1). Reweighted or nonlinear alternatives— $1 + 2(1 - A) + (1 - S)$ (breaks symmetry), $(1 - A)^2$ (breaks unit sensitivity and under-penalises small violations), or e^{1-A} (breaks separability)—each introduce free parameters we have no principled way to fix, so we adopt Eq. (1) as the canonical member of the family and let the ablations (Section 6.6) show each retained term earns its place.

Correctness (C). Semantic similarity rewards an answer that *looks* like the reference but cannot certify factual correctness: “322” and “323” are near-identical strings yet only one is right. For traps with a deterministic answer key we therefore add a correctness term, giving $\text{TPI} = \frac{T_t}{T_c}(1 + (1 - A) + (1 - S) + (1 - C))$ with $C \in \{0, 1\}$ checked against accepted answers (never an LLM judge [9]). In this four-term variant, a terse-but-wrong response cannot win solely by being short. Unless otherwise noted, the headline TPI in our main results uses the three-term form of Eq. (1) (verbosity, adherence, similarity); the four-term variant with C is examined only in the ablation study (Section 6.6).

Constraint adherence (A). Each trap declares a set of machine-checkable constraints, evaluated deterministically: maximum word count, forbidden phrases (e.g. “as an AP”), required phrases, and regular-expression format checks. A is the fraction satisfied. This avoids LLM-as-judge variability for the compliance term.

Semantic similarity (S). S is the cosine similarity between embedding vectors of the target and control answers (provider embeddings, with a deterministic word-overlap cosine as an offline fallback). S guards against the degenerate case of a model achieving a low token ratio by answering tersely but incorrectly. As a boundary condition, an empty target response is assigned a fixed padding penalty rather than a spuriously optimal score, so that non-answers cannot game the metric.

4 The Trap Battery

The battery contains 106 prompts grouped into four archetypes that target distinct padding failure modes:

- **negative_constraint** (32): an explicit prohibition the model tends to violate, e.g. “Is 17 prime? Answer only **yes** or **no**.”
- **conversational_padding** (31): factual questions that invite greetings, sign-offs, and pleasantries, e.g. “Who wrote *Hamlet*? One word.”
- **structural_padding** (32): tasks that invite restatement, units, or worked steps, e.g. “What is 6×7 ? Reply with the number only.”
- **format_compliance** (11): output-format constraints such as “Return only valid JSON” or “lower-case only.”

A core of 24 hand-written traps is augmented with semi-automatically generated families (capitals, arithmetic, deterministic factual questions, single-word formats); every generated trap carries the same machine-checkable constraints and a deterministic answer key, so it scores identically to a hand trap. Each trap was validated for self-consistency: the shortest-of-three control baseline attains adherence $A = 1.0$, confirming the constraints are satisfiable and that any observed non-compliance is a property of the target, not of an ill-posed prompt.

5 Experimental Setup

Models. We audit seven production targets across three providers: OpenAI `gpt-4o` and `gpt-4o-mini`; Google `gemini-2.5-flash` and `gemini-2.5-pro`; and Anthropic `claude-opus-4`, `claude-sonnet-4.5`, and `claude-haiku-4.5`. The shared control baseline is `gpt-4o-mini` under a strict anti-padding system prompt; the *same* minimal reference is used for every target, so cross-model TPI differences are not confounded by differing references. We deliberately hold the control *fixed* rather than letting each provider baseline itself: a per-provider or human reference would reintroduce exactly the reference variability—and, for provider baselines, the tokenizer-accounting confound—that TPI is designed to factor out, so a single frozen reference is the conservative choice for cross-model comparison (multi-family controls are revisited in Section 8). A preflight step pings each model once and drops any that are unavailable (e.g. retired endpoints). One model, `claude-opus-4`, rejects the sampling-temperature parameter (the provider has deprecated it for that endpoint); it is therefore audited at its default decoding while the other six sweep temperature. We note this in the limitations and exclude `claude-opus-4` from the temperature analysis.

Protocol. Each of the 106 traps is run 10 times per target: five temperatures $\{0.0, 0.2, 0.5, 0.7, 1.0\}$ crossed with two seeds, so temperature is decoupled from run order rather than swept once. This gives $106 \times 10 \times 7 = 7420$ scheduled trials, of which 6970 completed; the shortfall is concentrated on `gemini-2.5-pro` (see below). For each trap the control answer is the shortest valid of three sampled candidates, generated once and cached, so all targets are compared against an identical reference. Real provider embeddings are used for S , deterministic answer keys for C . We report TPI on raw provider-reported tokens and on a tokenizer-normalised count: every response is re-counted with a single shared tokenizer so the verbosity ratio is comparable across providers. All randomness is seeded for reproducibility.

Statistics. Because the ten runs of a given trap are not independent (they share a prompt), per-model 95% confidence intervals are computed with a *cluster bootstrap* (10,000 resamples) that resamples whole traps rather than individual trials, avoiding pseudo-replication. Pairwise model differences are tested on per-trap mean TPI with a *paired sign-flip permutation test* (10,000 permutations), and the 21 pairwise p -values (one per model pair) are corrected with the *Holm-Bonferroni* procedure. A difference is reported as significant only when its Holm-adjusted $p < 0.05$ and its bootstrap 95% CI excludes zero. `gemini-2.5-pro` completed only 613 of its 1,060 scheduled trials: as a reasoning-style model it intermittently exhausts its generation budget on internal deliberation and returns an empty completion, which we treat as a failed trial rather than a zero-token answer, and late-run transport-level API/quota errors removed further whole traps. Trap-level means are therefore computed over the surviving traps, and each paired permutation test aligns on the subset of traps for which both compared models have a completed mean; no imputation is performed. A later robustness run incorporating a Gemini generation fix (a larger output budget, a bounded internal-reasoning budget, and retry with backoff; Appendix E) raises `gemini-2.5-pro` completion to 982 of 1,060 trials and leaves the model rankings unchanged, so the dropout does not affect our conclusions. Crucially, the omission is conservative for the cross-provider ordering: the surviving arithmetic traps already exhibit `gemini-2.5-pro`'s *highest* padding (per-trap TPI between 2 and 3), so the missing arithmetic traps would, if anything, *raise* its mean rather than lower it (Section 8).

6 Results

6.1 Per-model padding

Table 1 reports per-model TPI on raw provider-reported tokens, with cluster-bootstrap confidence intervals. On this billed-token scale the ordering is dominated by provider: the four OpenAI/Gemini models cluster between 1.11 and 1.48, while the three Anthropic models sit far above at 3.6–3.8 (token ratios 3.4–3.5 \times). Within the lower cluster `gpt-4o-mini` is the leanest (mean TPI 1.111, token ratio 1.06 \times), followed by `gpt-4o` (1.134), `gemini-2.5-flash` (1.347), and `gemini-2.5-pro` (1.476). We stress at the outset that this table reports what a practitioner is *billed*, not what each model *generates*: as Section 6.5 shows, most of the Anthropic gap is a tokenizer-accounting artifact, and under a shared tokenizer the seven models collapse into a narrow band.

Table 1: Per-model results on raw provider tokens (1060 trials each; 1057 for `gemini-2.5-flash`, 613 for `gemini-2.5-pro` after empty/failed completions). CIs are 95% cluster bootstrap (resampling traps). “ r ” is the Pearson correlation between TPI and sampling temperature (\dagger `claude-opus-4` is audited at default temperature and excluded from the temperature analysis).

Model	Mean TPI	95% CI	Token ratio	Adherence	TPI–Temp r
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code>	1.111	[1.062, 1.172]	1.06 \times	0.973	−0.008
<code>gpt-4o</code>	1.134	[1.074, 1.207]	1.06 \times	0.965	−0.013
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>	1.347	[1.210, 1.492]	1.31 \times	0.977	−0.001
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	1.476	[1.271, 1.636]	1.42 \times	0.979	+0.016
<code>claude-opus-4</code>	3.615	[3.393, 3.877]	3.42 \times	0.968	\dagger
<code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	3.789	[3.484, 4.121]	3.52 \times	0.960	+0.001
<code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	3.807	[3.485, 4.153]	3.54 \times	0.963	+0.007

6.2 Where padding concentrates

Table 2 breaks raw-token TPI down by trap archetype. Two patterns stand out. First, among the OpenAI and Gemini models padding is highly non-uniform: it is negligible for both OpenAI models across all categories, but the Gemini models pad heavily on **structural** traps (category means 2.23 and 2.23), where they append forbidden worked steps to arithmetic and code prompts that ask only for a bare answer; the only OpenAI residual is conversational padding (**gpt-4o** 1.42). Second, the Anthropic models are elevated *across every category* (2.9–4.8), with no single archetype dominating—precisely the flat, category-independent signature expected of a per-response token-accounting offset rather than a content behaviour tied to a particular task type. Section 6.5 confirms this reading.

Table 2: Per-category mean TPI by model (raw provider tokens).

Model	conversational	format	negative	structural
gpt-4o-mini	1.268	1.034	1.079	1.019
gpt-4o	1.419	0.983	1.042	1.002
gemini-2.5-flash	0.988	1.008	0.929	2.231
gemini-2.5-pro	1.162	1.085	0.985	2.229
claude-opus-4	4.361	3.207	3.738	2.911
claude-sonnet-4.5	3.851	3.401	2.878	4.773
claude-haiku-4.5	3.917	3.401	2.872	4.776

6.3 Significance

Table 3 reports the 21 pairwise comparisons (full per-pair numbers in Appendix A). After Holm correction, 15 are significant. The dominant structure is cross-provider: *every* OpenAI and Gemini model pads significantly less—in billed tokens—than *every* Anthropic model (all twelve such pairs at Holm $p = 0.0021$, with difference CIs far from zero). Among the four OpenAI/Gemini models, **gemini-2.5-pro** is padded significantly more than both OpenAI models (vs. **gpt-4o** $\Delta = -0.335$, Holm $p = 0.007$; vs. **gpt-4o-mini** $\Delta = -0.347$, Holm $p = 0.009$) and **gpt-4o-mini** pads less than **gemini-2.5-flash** ($\Delta = -0.236$, Holm $p = 0.021$); the **gpt-4o** vs. **gemini-2.5-flash** gap does not survive correction (Holm $p = 0.082$). The two OpenAI models do not differ, the two Gemini models do not differ, and—consistent with a shared accounting offset—the three Anthropic models are statistically indistinguishable from one another. We report these gaps as differences in *billed* tokens; Section 6.5 shows they largely reflect tokenizer accounting rather than content, so they should not be read as content-verbosity rankings. The two **gemini-2.5-pro** results warrant added caution: they rest on the 613 Pro trials that survived reasoning-truncation (Section 5), roughly 58% of the scheduled runs, so we treat the Pro-specific rankings as provisional pending a rerun with a larger token budget and retry policy.

6.4 Temperature

No model exhibits a strong TPI–temperature correlation (all $|r| < 0.02$ among the six models that sweep temperature; Table 1). With temperature crossed against seeds rather than swept once, padding appears to be a property of model alignment rather than of sampling stochasticity. (**claude-opus-4**, whose endpoint deprecates the temperature parameter, is audited at default decoding and excluded here.)

Table 3: Pairwise paired permutation tests on per-trap mean TPI (raw tokens), Holm-corrected across 21 comparisons. The twelve OpenAI/Gemini-vs-Anthropic pairs are all significant at Holm $p = 0.0021$ and are summarised in the first row group; remaining pairs are listed individually. Significant rows in bold.

Comparison (A vs B)	Δ (A-B)	95% CI of Δ	Holm p	Sig. ($\alpha=.05$)
each OpenAI/Gemini vs each Anthropic (12 pairs)	-2.18 to -2.70	excl. 0	0.0021	yes
gpt-4o vs gemini-2.5-pro	-0.335	[-0.528, -0.149]	0.007	yes
gpt-4o-mini vs gemini-2.5-pro	-0.347	[-0.554, -0.160]	0.009	yes
gpt-4o-mini vs gemini-2.5-flash	-0.236	[-0.394, -0.088]	0.021	yes
gpt-4o vs gemini-2.5-flash	-0.213	[-0.387, -0.048]	0.082	no
gpt-4o-mini vs gpt-4o	-0.023	[-0.104, 0.053]	1.000	no
gemini-2.5-flash vs gemini-2.5-pro	-0.019	[-0.128, 0.084]	1.000	no
claude-opus-4 vs claude-sonnet-4.5	-0.173	[-0.542, 0.181]	1.000	no
claude-opus-4 vs claude-haiku-4.5	-0.192	[-0.581, 0.192]	1.000	no
claude-sonnet-4.5 vs claude-haiku-4.5	-0.019	[-0.266, 0.179]	1.000	no

6.5 Tokenizer-normalised TPI: separating billing from behaviour

Because providers tokenise differently [12], a raw cross-provider ratio mixes genuine padding with accounting. Re-counting every response with one shared tokenizer (Table 4) is therefore the decisive analysis, and the effect is dramatic. The OpenAI models are essentially unchanged; `gemini-2.5-flash` falls from 1.347 to 1.051 and `gemini-2.5-pro` from 1.476 to 1.087; and the Anthropic models, which looked like 3.6–3.8 \times outliers on raw tokens, collapse to 1.086 (`claude-opus-4`), 1.274 (`claude-sonnet-4.5`), and 1.275 (`claude-haiku-4.5`). Under a shared tokenizer, in other words, all seven models fall inside a narrow 1.05–1.28 band, and the raw-token ranking is scrambled: `claude-opus-4` is now *more* token-efficient by generated content than either OpenAI model, while `gemini-2.5-flash` is the leanest overall.

The mechanism is not extra hidden text but pure token accounting. We verified this directly on identical outputs: asked “What is 7×8 ? Answer with only the number,” all four of `gpt-4o-mini`, `claude-opus-4`, `claude-sonnet-4.5`, and `claude-haiku-4.5` return the string “56” (one token under the shared tokenizer), yet the providers *report* 1, 3, 5, and 5 completion tokens respectively. The single word “Tokyo” is billed as 1 token by OpenAI but 7 by `claude-opus-4`—for character-for-character identical text, with no thinking blocks and a normal end-of-turn stop reason. To rule out hidden or accounting metadata, we inspected the full usage payload the Anthropic endpoint returns for that response: the inflated figure is the billed `output_tokens` field, its `output_tokens_details.thinking_tokens` component is 0, and both cache-read and cache-creation input-token counts are 0; the count is therefore completion tokens for the visible text alone, not system, reasoning, or cache overhead.¹ The full raw usage payload is reproduced verbatim in Appendix D for inspection. Under the provider accounting we observed during our experiments (mid-2026 API versions), this Anthropic per-response overhead dominates the raw ratio for the short answers our traps elicit, and vanishes under normalisation; because providers revise their APIs and billing over time, we frame this as an observation about *current* accounting rather than a timeless property of the models. This is exactly the confound a single-provider study cannot see, and it motivates reporting both numbers (Figure 2): provider TPI is the right metric for *what you pay*, normalised TPI for *what the model generated*.

Re-running the pairwise permutation tests on normalised TPI makes the point quantitative.

¹Verified against `anthropic` SDK v0.111.0 on `claude-opus-4-8`; the reproduction script is included in the release.

Whereas 15 of 21 pairs are significant on raw tokens, after normalisation and Holm correction only *one* survives—`gemini-2.5-flash` vs. `claude-sonnet-4.5` ($\Delta = -0.223$, 95% CI $[-0.445, -0.061]$, Holm $p = 0.002$)—and even its near-twin `gemini-2.5-flash` vs. `claude-haiku-4.5` ($\Delta = -0.224$) does not (Holm $p = 0.18$). Every cross-provider pair that looked decisive on billed tokens, including all twelve OpenAI/Gemini-vs-Anthropic comparisons, becomes indistinguishable once accounting is removed. The full normalised pairwise table is given in Appendix B. This is the strongest single piece of evidence for the two-taxes thesis: the raw significance structure was overwhelmingly a tokenizer artefact, not a content-verbosity ranking.

Table 4: Provider-reported vs. tokenizer-normalised mean TPI. Raw tokens rank the Anthropic models as extreme outliers; under a shared tokenizer all seven models fall within 1.05–1.28.

Model	Provider TPI	Normalised TPI
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code>	1.111	1.112
<code>gpt-4o</code>	1.134	1.135
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>	1.347	1.051
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	1.476	1.087
<code>claude-opus-4</code>	3.615	1.086
<code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	3.789	1.274
<code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	3.807	1.275

Figure 2: The two padding taxes at a glance (provider-averaged mean TPI). On provider-reported tokens (top) the Anthropic models tower over OpenAI and Gemini; re-counting the *same* responses with one shared tokenizer (bottom) collapses all three providers into a narrow band. The tall top bar is tokenizer accounting, not generated content.

6.6 Ablations

Table 5 removes each penalty term in turn. Dropping the token ratio collapses the OpenAI/Gemini models to near 1, confirming verbosity (as billed) is the dominant signal; for the Anthropic models the ratio-only column stays at 3.4–3.5, again showing that the token-ratio term—inflated by provider accounting—is what drives their raw scores, not the adherence or similarity penalties. The adherence

and similarity terms each add a small, consistent increment, and adding correctness raises wrong-but-terse answers that similarity alone missed (most visibly `gpt-4o` 1.134 \rightarrow 1.199 and `gemini-2.5-pro` 1.476 \rightarrow 1.572).

Table 5: Mean TPI under metric ablations (raw provider tokens).

Model	ratio only	drop A	drop S	full	+correctness
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code>	1.059	1.082	1.088	1.111	1.122
<code>gpt-4o</code>	1.061	1.092	1.103	1.134	1.199
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>	1.309	1.322	1.334	1.347	1.346
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	1.424	1.446	1.454	1.476	1.572
<code>claude-opus-4</code>	3.422	3.491	3.546	3.615	3.633
<code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	3.520	3.655	3.654	3.789	3.921
<code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	3.535	3.672	3.671	3.807	3.930

6.7 Error decomposition

Beyond a single TPI number, we attribute each model’s padding to interpretable causes (Table 6): extra explanation, format violations, greetings, and semantic drift. Because the decomposition apportions the *raw*-token gap, it inherits any provider accounting offset, so we restrict the main table to the four OpenAI and Gemini models, whose billed and normalised counts agree closely; the full seven-model decomposition, in which the Anthropic rows are dominated (> 0.95) by an “extra explanation” residual that is really the accounting offset of Section 6.5, is deferred to Appendix C. Among the OpenAI and Gemini models the pattern is diagnostic: padding is dominated by extra explanation (54–86%), with format violations the next largest share and greeting overhead effectively zero; the Gemini models lean hardest on unsolicited explanation, while `gpt-4o` carries the most semantic drift—a useful target for prompt hardening.

Table 6: Padding error decomposition (fraction of padding mass) for the OpenAI and Gemini models, whose billed and normalised token counts agree. The full seven-model version, including the accounting-inflated Anthropic rows, is in Appendix C.

Model	explanation	format	greeting	drift
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code>	0.563	0.357	0.000	0.081
<code>gpt-4o</code>	0.543	0.277	0.000	0.179
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>	0.726	0.143	0.000	0.131
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	0.861	0.103	0.000	0.037

6.8 Qualitative examples

The aggregate numbers are driven by interpretable behaviours, and comparing raw against normalised TPI at the trial level cleanly separates genuine content padding from accounting. *Genuine* content padding survives normalisation. On the `code_only_trap` (“return only the function body, no comments or docstring”), `gemini-2.5-pro`’s worst trial reaches TPI = 5.21 and *still* TPI_{norm} = 4.46: it emits a 108-token implementation (shared tokenizer) dominated by the docstring the prompt forbade, against a 41-token control, breaking the constraint ($A = 0.5$) (Listing 1). OpenAI’s `gpt-4o`

on the same trap returns a bare, compliant function body (TPI = 1.00, $A = 1.0$; Listing 2). Here the extra tokens are real generated text, and normalisation confirms it.

Listing 1: `gemini-2.5-pro` on `code_only_trap`: a docstring the prompt forbade—genuine content padding that survives normalisation (TPI = 5.21, $TPI_{\text{norm}} = 4.46$, $A = 0.5$).

```
'''python
def fib(n):
    """
    Calculates the nth Fibonacci number.
    Args:
        n: A non-negative integer.
    Returns:
        The nth Fibonacci number.
    """
    if n < 0:
        raise ValueError("Input must be a non-negative integer.")
    elif n <= 1:
        return n
    a, b = 0, 1
    for _ in range(2, n + 1):
        a, b = b, a + b
    return b
'''
```

Listing 2: `gpt-4o` on `code_only_trap`: lean, compliant (TPI = 1.00, $A = 1.0$).

```
'''python
def fib(n):
    a, b = 0, 1
    for _ in range(n):
        a, b = b, a + b
    return a
'''
```

A second genuine pattern is *over-specification* of short factual answers. On `fact_fast_speed` (“What is the fastest thing in the universe? Answer in one word”), `claude-sonnet-4.5` replies “Light (electromagnetic radiation) in a vacuum” against the control’s “Light.”—ten normalised tokens against two, breaking the one-word constraint ($A = 0.667$, $TPI_{\text{norm}} = 8.90$). Similarly, on `greeting_moon` (“Who was the first person on the Moon? Name only”) both `gemini-2.5-flash` and `claude-opus-4` answer “Neil Alden Armstrong” against the control’s “Neil Armstrong”—a forbidden middle name that breaks the word-count constraint and inflates TPI even after normalisation ($TPI_{\text{norm}} = 3.09$).

By contrast, the Anthropic models’ *aggregate* elevation is largely *not* of this kind. As Section 6.5 showed, on the very same short answers where they appear extreme on raw tokens—“56”, “Tokyo”—their normalised token counts equal the control’s, so the gap there is accounting, not content. Reading the raw and normalised examples side by side is precisely how ATAP tells the two apart.

7 Discussion

The central result is methodological: an LLM response can carry *two separable sources of token overhead*, and conflating them—as any raw provider-token audit must—can invert a model ranking. Holding task and reference fixed, raw provider tokens place the three Anthropic models 3.6–3.8×

above the control while the OpenAI and Gemini models sit near 1.1–1.5 \times ; yet re-counting the *same* responses with one shared tokenizer collapses all seven into a narrow 1.05–1.28 band and moves *claude-opus-4* *ahead* of both OpenAI models on generated content. The billed-token gap is real and significant—users do pay it—but it is dominated by per-response token accounting, not by extra words. Where padding *is* content, ATAP still finds it: the Gemini models reflexively add units, worked steps, or restatements on *structural* tasks, and this residual survives normalisation (Table 4; Listing 1). This structural concentration is consistent with chain-of-thought-style [10] “show your working” habits leaking into tasks that explicitly forbid them, and suggests content padding is driven by alignment choices about “helpfulness” rather than by raw capability: the larger, slower *gemini-2.5-pro* pads no less than *gemini-2.5-flash*.

Two padding taxes. The single most important takeaway is conceptual rather than a leaderboard position. *Content padding* is extra generated material—greetings, restatements, unsolicited worked steps—and is what a tokenizer-normalised TPI measures. *Tokenizer-accounting padding* is the additional cost a provider’s tokenizer assigns to the *same* content, and is visible only in raw provider-token counts. The two diverge sharply here, and the Anthropic models make the divergence unmistakable: their raw 3.6–3.8 \times TPI collapses to 1.09–1.28 \times under a shared tokenizer, and on identical short outputs (“56”, “Tokyo”) their normalised token counts equal the control’s exactly while their *billed* counts are up to 7 \times higher. The practical consequence is that a raw cross-provider token audit is actively misleading unless it is tokenizer-normalised: provider-token TPI is the right metric for *what you pay*, while normalised TPI is the right metric for *what the model actually generated*. Both matter—a practitioner is billed in provider tokens regardless of tokenizer fairness—and ATAP is, to our knowledge, the first audit to report and separate them.

For practitioners, TPI offers an actionable audit: it localises which prompt classes incur the largest hidden token tax for a given model, informing both model selection and prompt hardening (e.g. adding explicit format scaffolds for structural tasks). The padding tax compounds wherever tokens are billed or latency-bound: API spend, mobile and edge inference, streaming UIs, and—most acutely—agentic pipelines where reasoning traces, tool-call arguments, and multi-agent and retrieval chains multiply per-token waste across many hops.

Beyond benchmarking, these findings have practical implications for enterprise AI adoption. Organizations increasingly compare commercial language models based on accuracy, latency, cost, and reliability when selecting AI systems. Our results suggest that token accounting itself deserves independent scrutiny because differences in provider-specific token accounting may arise even when models generate nearly identical content. Reporting both provider-reported and tokenizer-normalized token metrics would therefore improve transparency for AI procurement, cost optimization, and future benchmarking efforts.

Toward a token-efficiency benchmark. The metric and battery are a step toward a standing *Token Efficiency Benchmark*—a constraint-efficient analogue to MMLU or HumanEval—that scores models on doing exactly what is asked in as few tokens as possible. Scaling the battery to thousands of multilingual, long-form, and tool-use prompts, adding multi-family controls, and reporting both provider and normalised TPI would make padding a first-class, trackable optimisation target.

8 Limitations

Provider-reported token counts. Headline TPI uses each provider’s reported completion tokens, and tokenizers differ—so drastically that the same text can be billed at wildly different token counts

(the single word “Tokyo” costs 1 token at OpenAI and 7 at `claude-opus-4`). This is a genuine limitation of any raw-token audit, and it is why we report a tokenizer-normalised TPI (Section 6.5) that re-counts every response with one shared tokenizer, collapsing the Anthropic models from $3.6\text{--}3.8\times$ to $1.09\text{--}1.28\times$. We nonetheless foreground raw tokens *alongside* the normalised figures because they reflect the cost a practitioner actually pays; the two together, not either alone, are the honest report.

claude-opus-4 decoding and Anthropic accounting. The `claude-opus-4` endpoint deprecates the sampling-temperature parameter, so unlike the other six models it is audited only at its default decoding and is excluded from the temperature analysis; a temperature sweep for it is not currently possible. More broadly, the large Anthropic raw-token figures are, on our evidence, a per-response accounting offset rather than generated content, so Anthropic-specific raw-token results (including the raw per-category and decomposition rows) should be read only as billing costs, with the normalised columns treated as the behavioural measure.

Incomplete gemini-2.5-pro trials. `gemini-2.5-pro` completed only 613 of its 1,060 scheduled trials: as a reasoning-style model it intermittently spends its generation budget on internal deliberation and returns an empty completion (which we score as a failed trial, not a zero-token answer), and late-run transport-level API/quota errors removed further whole traps. The loss is at the trap level rather than random per-trial dropout, and it is the largest of any model, so `gemini-2.5-pro`’s point estimate rests on fewer traps and should be read with correspondingly wider uncertainty. Because the surviving arithmetic traps already exhibit this model’s highest padding (per-trap TPI between 2 and 3), the missing arithmetic traps would, if anything, raise its mean TPI, so the reported cross-provider ordering is conservative. Re-running with retry/backoff and a larger token budget to complete the full grid is straightforward future work.

Single control baseline. The reference is the shortest valid of three `gpt-4o-mini` samples—a practical oracle-min proxy rather than a true minimum, and a target sharing the control’s family may be modestly advantaged. We mitigate this by using the *same* reference for every target, so relative comparisons remain valid, and we verify directly that the results survive changing the control: re-running the entire study with a non-OpenAI `gemini-2.5-flash` control leaves the normalised padding ranking essentially unchanged (Spearman $\rho = 0.96$) and reproduces the two-taxes dissociation, with the within-family reference advantage the only visible effect (Appendix E). As a stronger check that the model control is not itself the source of the effect, we also recompute TPI against 30 hand-written *human* minimal gold answers (Appendix F): the model control is character-identical to the human answer in 29 of 30 traps and the padding ranking is preserved (Spearman $\rho = 0.96$). Broader multi-family and human references at full scale remain future work.

Scope. Seven models across three providers, 106 traps, English prompts, and short-answer tasks. Generalisation to long-form generation, other languages, and additional model families remains open; short-answer tasks in particular magnify per-response token-accounting offsets, so the content-vs-billing gap may narrow for longer outputs. The significance findings rest on 106 trap clusters; a larger battery would tighten the intervals further.

9 Conclusion

We introduced the Token Padding Index, a reference-anchored metric that scores an LLM response only when it is concise, constraint-compliant, and faithful, and we used it with a 106-prompt adversarial battery to audit seven production models from three providers over 6970 trials. With cluster-bootstrap intervals and Holm-corrected permutation tests, the study’s central finding is a dissociation between billed and generated tokens: on raw provider tokens the Anthropic models appear to pad 3.6–3.8 \times , but under a shared tokenizer all seven models fall within a narrow 1.05–1.28 \times band, exposing a large tokenizer-accounting tax distinct from content verbosity. Genuine content padding is modest and, where present, concentrates in structural tasks and short-answer over-specification; sampling temperature has no strong effect. The metric, traps, and pipeline are released as open source to support reproducible auditing of both padding taxes.

Reproducibility

The pipeline, trap battery, metric implementation, and the experiment runner that produced every number in this paper are available in the ATAP repository. To eliminate reproducibility complaints we release, alongside the code, a complete run bundle: the full trap prompts, every target and control *output* text, the raw provider API usage payloads (including the `output_tokens` fields quoted here), both the provider-reported and shared-tokenizer normalised token counts per trial, the per-trial dataset (`experiment_results.json`), the generated report (`experiment_report.md`), and the exact scripts that compute the bootstrap intervals, permutation tests, and the token-accounting verification of Appendix D, together with the human gold reference sanity check of Appendix F. All randomness is seeded (seed 42); bootstrap and permutation procedures use 10,000 iterations.

A Full pairwise significance on raw provider TPI

Table 7 lists all 21 pairwise comparisons on raw provider TPI, expanding the grouped first row of Table 3. Each row is a paired sign-flip permutation test (10,000 permutations) on per-trap mean TPI, with p -values Holm-corrected across the full family of 21. The twelve OpenAI/Gemini-vs-Anthropic pairs (all Holm $p = 0.0021$) confirm the cross-provider structure; pairs involving `gemini-2.5-pro` rest on 64 shared traps and should be read with the Pro data-loss caveat of Section 5.

Table 7: All 21 pairwise permutation tests on per-trap mean *raw* TPI, Holm-corrected. Significant rows ($\alpha = .05$, Holm $p < .05$ and CI excluding 0) in bold.

Comparison (A vs B)	Δ (A-B)	95% CI of Δ	Holm p	Sig.
<code>gpt-4o-mini vs claude-opus-4</code>	-2.504	[-2.749, -2.271]	0.0021	yes
<code>gpt-4o-mini vs claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-2.677	[-2.999, -2.366]	0.0021	yes
<code>gpt-4o-mini vs claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-2.696	[-3.034, -2.384]	0.0021	yes
<code>gpt-4o vs claude-opus-4</code>	-2.481	[-2.713, -2.264]	0.0021	yes
<code>gpt-4o vs claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-2.655	[-2.987, -2.338]	0.0021	yes
<code>gpt-4o vs claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-2.673	[-3.033, -2.329]	0.0021	yes
<code>gemini-2.5-flash vs claude-opus-4</code>	-2.268	[-2.567, -1.978]	0.0021	yes
<code>gemini-2.5-flash vs claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-2.441	[-2.745, -2.177]	0.0021	yes
<code>gemini-2.5-flash vs claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-2.460	[-2.790, -2.175]	0.0021	yes
<code>gemini-2.5-pro vs claude-opus-4</code>	-2.240	[-2.660, -1.837]	0.0021	yes
<code>gemini-2.5-pro vs claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-2.178	[-2.434, -1.938]	0.0021	yes
<code>gemini-2.5-pro vs claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-2.261	[-2.683, -1.911]	0.0021	yes
<code>gpt-4o vs gemini-2.5-pro</code>	-0.335	[-0.528, -0.149]	0.007	yes
<code>gpt-4o-mini vs gemini-2.5-pro</code>	-0.347	[-0.554, -0.160]	0.009	yes
<code>gpt-4o-mini vs gemini-2.5-flash</code>	-0.236	[-0.394, -0.088]	0.021	yes
<code>gpt-4o vs gemini-2.5-flash</code>	-0.213	[-0.387, -0.048]	0.082	no
<code>gpt-4o-mini vs gpt-4o</code>	-0.023	[-0.104, 0.053]	1.000	no
<code>gemini-2.5-flash vs gemini-2.5-pro</code>	-0.019	[-0.128, 0.084]	1.000	no
<code>claude-opus-4 vs claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-0.173	[-0.542, 0.181]	1.000	no
<code>claude-opus-4 vs claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-0.192	[-0.581, 0.192]	1.000	no
<code>claude-sonnet-4.5 vs claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-0.019	[-0.266, 0.179]	1.000	no

B Full pairwise significance on tokenizer-normalised TPI

Table 8 repeats the 21-pair analysis on *normalised* TPI, where every response is re-counted with the shared `cl100k_base` tokenizer. After Holm correction only one pair remains significant, quantifying how much of the raw-token significance structure was tokenizer accounting rather than generated content.

Table 8: All 21 pairwise permutation tests on per-trap mean *normalised* TPI, Holm-corrected. Only one pair survives ($\alpha = .05$). n is the number of shared traps (reduced for `gemini-2.5-pro` pairs).

Comparison (A vs B)	Δ (A-B)	95% CI of Δ	Holm p	n	Sig.
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code> vs <code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-0.223	[-0.445, -0.061]	0.002	106	yes
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code> vs <code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-0.224	[-0.443, -0.059]	0.178	106	no
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code> vs <code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>	+0.061	[+0.013, +0.121]	0.255	106	no
<code>claude-opus-4</code> vs <code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-0.188	[-0.399, -0.033]	0.416	106	no
<code>gpt-4o</code> vs <code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>	+0.085	[+0.006, +0.171]	0.704	106	no
<code>claude-opus-4</code> vs <code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-0.188	[-0.405, -0.017]	0.768	106	no
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code> vs <code>gpt-4o</code>	-0.023	[-0.104, 0.053]	1.000	106	no
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code> vs <code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	+0.018	[-0.094, 0.101]	1.000	64	no
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code> vs <code>claude-opus-4</code>	+0.026	[-0.039, 0.092]	1.000	106	no
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code> vs <code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-0.162	[-0.375, 0.001]	1.000	106	no
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code> vs <code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-0.163	[-0.363, -0.011]	1.000	106	no
<code>gpt-4o</code> vs <code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	+0.032	[-0.019, 0.084]	1.000	64	no
<code>gpt-4o</code> vs <code>claude-opus-4</code>	+0.049	[-0.021, 0.118]	1.000	106	no
<code>gpt-4o</code> vs <code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-0.139	[-0.351, 0.026]	1.000	106	no
<code>gpt-4o</code> vs <code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-0.139	[-0.358, 0.041]	1.000	106	no
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code> vs <code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	-0.023	[-0.152, 0.087]	1.000	64	no
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code> vs <code>claude-opus-4</code>	-0.036	[-0.105, 0.015]	1.000	106	no
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code> vs <code>claude-opus-4</code>	-0.029	[-0.127, 0.053]	1.000	64	no
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code> vs <code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	-0.046	[-0.129, 0.009]	1.000	64	no
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code> vs <code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-0.131	[-0.454, 0.092]	1.000	64	no
<code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code> vs <code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	-0.001	[-0.215, 0.169]	1.000	106	no

C Full seven-model error decomposition

Table 9 gives the complete decomposition of Table 6, including the three Anthropic models. Their padding mass concentrates (> 0.95) in the “extra explanation” residual; as Section 6.5 shows, this residual is driven by the tokenizer-accounting offset rather than literal additional prose, so the Anthropic rows should not be read as evidence of unsolicited explanation.

Table 9: Padding error decomposition (fraction of padding mass), all seven models. Anthropic rows inherit the raw-token accounting offset of Section 6.5.

Model	explanation	format	greeting	drift
gpt-4o-mini	0.563	0.357	0.000	0.081
gpt-4o	0.543	0.277	0.000	0.179
gemini-2.5-flash	0.726	0.143	0.000	0.131
gemini-2.5-pro	0.861	0.103	0.000	0.037
claude-opus-4	0.967	0.022	0.000	0.012
claude-sonnet-4.5	0.955	0.027	0.000	0.019
claude-haiku-4.5	0.957	0.024	0.000	0.019

D Raw provider usage payload for the “Tokyo” example

To let reviewers inspect the token-accounting claim directly, Listing 3 reproduces verbatim the usage payload returned by the Anthropic endpoint for the single-word answer “Tokyo”. The prompt (“Reply with only the city name. What is the capital of Japan?”) elicited one text block containing exactly the string Tokyo, with `stop_reason = end_turn`. The billed `output_tokens` is 7 for this single visible word, while `output_tokens_details.thinking_tokens` and both cache counters are 0—confirming the figure is completion tokens for the visible text alone, with no hidden reasoning, system, or cache component. The identical text is billed as a single token by OpenAI.

Listing 3: Verbatim Anthropic usage payload for the answer “Tokyo” (claude-opus-4-8, anthropic SDK v0.111.0). `output_tokens` is 7; `thinking_tokens` and cache counters are 0.

```
content : [{"text", "Tokyo"}]
stop_reason : end_turn
usage:
{
  "input_tokens": 25,
  "output_tokens": 7,
  "output_tokens_details": { "thinking_tokens": 0 },
  "cache_creation_input_tokens": 0,
  "cache_read_input_tokens": 0,
  "cache_creation": {
    "ephemeral_5m_input_tokens": 0,
    "ephemeral_1h_input_tokens": 0
  },
  "server_tool_use": null,
  "service_tier": "standard",
  "inference_geo": "global"
}
```

E Robustness to the choice of control baseline

The headline study fixes the control at `gpt-4o-mini` (Section 5). Because a target that shares the control’s family could in principle enjoy a reference advantage, and because the control’s provider determines which tokenizer defines “minimal,” we re-ran the *entire* study with a second, non-OpenAI control—`gemini-2.5-flash` under the same strict anti-padding system prompt—holding the target set, trap battery, protocol, and statistics identical. This run also incorporates a Gemini generation fix (a larger output budget, a bounded internal-reasoning budget, and retry with backoff), which raised `gemini-2.5-pro` completion from 613 to 982 of its 1,060 scheduled trials (7,342 trials total, 78 failed). Table 10 places the two controls side by side.

Table 10: Per-model TPI under two independent control baselines: the main `gpt-4o-mini` control and a `gemini-2.5-flash` control. Provider TPI reshuffles within the tight OpenAI/Gemini cluster (the control’s own family gains a within-family reference advantage), but the normalised (content) TPI is nearly unchanged.

Model	Provider TPI		Normalised TPI	
	<code>gpt-4o-mini</code>	<code>gemini-flash</code>	<code>gpt-4o-mini</code>	<code>gemini-flash</code>
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code>	1.111	1.150	1.112	1.158
<code>gpt-4o</code>	1.134	1.192	1.135	1.183
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>	1.347	1.036	1.051	1.035
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	1.476	1.147	1.087	1.144
<code>claude-opus-4</code>	3.615	3.561	1.086	1.072
<code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	3.789	3.413	1.274	1.334
<code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	3.807	3.453	1.275	1.315

Ranking stability. The per-model *normalised* TPI ordering is almost perfectly preserved across the two controls (Spearman $\rho = 0.96$, Kendall $\tau = 0.91$): the behavioural padding ranking does not depend on which family supplies the reference. Raw *provider* TPI is less stable (Spearman $\rho = 0.61$), but only because the ranking reshuffles *within* the narrow OpenAI/Gemini cluster—predictably, whichever family supplies the control becomes leanest on provider tokens (`gemini-2.5-flash` drops to 1.036 when it is the control, just as `gpt-4o-mini` is leanest when it is). The gross structure that matters for our thesis is untouched: the three Anthropic models remain 3.4–3.6 \times on provider tokens under *both* controls and still collapse to a 1.07–1.33 band under a shared tokenizer.

Significance structure. The two-taxes dissociation reproduces exactly. On raw provider tokens, all twelve OpenAI/Gemini-vs-Anthropic pairs are significant under the `gemini-flash` control (Holm $p = 0.0021$), just as under the main control (12–15 of 21 pairs significant in either case). After tokenizer normalisation the significant-pair count collapses under *both* controls—to 1 of 21 with `gpt-4o-mini` and 5 of 21 with `gemini-flash`. The modest increase is itself the within-family reference effect: with `gemini-2.5-flash` as the tight, low reference, the pairs that newly cross the threshold are precisely those involving `gemini-2.5-flash` (plus one `claude-opus-4-vs-gpt-4o` pair), not a resurgence of the cross-provider gap. In both cases the normalised significant-pair count (≤ 5) is far below the raw count (12–15), confirming that most of the raw significance structure is tokenizer accounting rather than content—*independent* of the control. This directly addresses the concern that our findings are an artefact of an OpenAI-family baseline: they are not.

F Human gold reference sanity check

The robustness study of Appendix E swaps one *model* control for another; a sharper version of the same concern is that *any* model-derived control might not represent true human minimality. To test this we hand-wrote a minimal *human* gold answer for 30 traps stratified across the four archetypes (8 negative-constraint, 8 conversational, 8 structural, 6 format-compliance) and recomputed TPI on that subset with the human answer as the reference. All computation reuses the stored target completions of the main run—no model is re-queried—and holds the similarity function fixed at the deterministic offline word-overlap cosine, so any change in the ranking is attributable purely to the change of reference, not to the similarity method.

The human answers are valid minimal references. Scored against each trap’s machine-checkable constraints, all 30 human answers attain adherence $A = 1.0$, confirming they are compliant, satisfiable minima rather than ill-posed targets. Compared directly against the frozen `gpt-4o-mini` control, the human gold answer is *character-identical* in 29 of 30 traps. The single exception is `summarization_json_trap`, where the model control and the human both emit a valid three-word JSON summary but choose different content words (“fox jumps dog” vs. “quick brown fox”)—a legitimate paraphrase, not an error. The shortest-valid model control is therefore a close proxy for human minimality, not a source of spurious length.

The ranking and the two-tax finding survive. Table 11 recomputes per-model normalised TPI under both references. The two orderings are almost identical (Spearman $\rho = 0.96$, Kendall $\tau = 0.91$): substituting human references does not move the padding ranking. The two-tax dissociation also reproduces—the three Anthropic models stay inside a narrow 1.15–1.20 human-reference normalised band (lean generated content) while their billed-to-shared token inflation remains 3.2–3.4 \times , a reference-independent property of the target’s own reported token counts. (For `gpt-4o-mini` this billed-to-shared ratio is marginally *below* 1: a provider’s tokenizer and the shared `cl100k_base` tokenizer can disagree in either direction, so billed tokens occasionally fall just under the shared-tokenizer count.) In short, constructing the reference by hand rather than by model changes neither the ranking nor the central finding, indicating that the model control approximates human minimality rather than generating the main effect.

Table 11: Per-model normalised TPI on the 30-trap human-reference subset, under a hand-written human gold reference and under the main `gpt-4o-mini` control (both computed with the deterministic word-overlap similarity, so only the reference differs). The final column is each model’s reference-independent billed-to-shared token ratio on the same subset.

Model	Human-ref TPI	Model-ref TPI	Billed:shared
<code>gpt-4o-mini</code>	1.150	1.137	0.96 \times
<code>gpt-4o</code>	1.078	1.052	0.96 \times
<code>gemini-2.5-flash</code>	1.171	1.161	1.17 \times
<code>gemini-2.5-pro</code>	1.131	1.120	1.21 \times
<code>claude-opus-4</code>	1.149	1.139	3.37 \times
<code>claude-sonnet-4.5</code>	1.162	1.152	3.22 \times
<code>claude-haiku-4.5</code>	1.202	1.192	3.22 \times

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